

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF FOOD SERVICE BUSINESS JOB DEMANDS ON MENTAL HEALTH (JDR MODEL): CASE OF FOREIGN WORKERS IN NORTH CYPRUS

Sultanov O.

Master of Science in Marketing

Independent Researcher

Baku, Azerbaijan

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Abstract

It is evident that a large-scale industry of tourism has a lot to offer to holidaymakers, travellers and consumers. However, when it comes to offering services to clientele, the hardships service providers go through cannot be ignored. Although many studies have focused on the employee experiences in hotel industry, the restaurant industry employee experiences and working circumstances have not been researched a lot, especially in terms of how their mental health is being affected. Therefore, this study sheds light on this matter by studying the impact of food and service business job demands on mental health of foreign workers in North Cyprus, while focusing on JDR (Job Demand-Resources) model. This research employs the JDR model to examine the moderating effect of job resources (Perceived Organizational Support-POS) on the relationship between job demands (Unscheduled Work (UW), Work Interference with Personal Life (WIP), Work Pressure (WP) and Adverse Working Conditions (AWCs) and mental health (Anxiety, Depression and Emotional Exhaustion (EE)). Thus, the research findings showed that job demands have an impact on mental health of foreign employees in North Cyprus. Moreover, the buffering effect of perceived organizational support was also found, which suggested that employees who received organizational support had lower impact of job demands on their mental health than the ones without an organizational support.

Keywords: Unscheduled Work (UW), Work Interference with Personal Life (WIP), Work Pressure (WP), Adverse Working Conditions (AWCs), Emotional Exhaustion (EE).

Introduction & Background. Globally 90 percent of restaurant workers are going through mental health problems and addiction issues [1]. Thus, the main reasons behind it are overwhelming and difficult working conditions, inconstant income, lack of additional perquisites and many others. Moreover, according to a survey conducted by “Heirloom Foundation” 73 percent of chefs that took part in the survey had mental health issues ranging from depression, anxiety, to drug addiction [2]. The main reasons behind these terrible mental states of food and beverage employees’ mental health were said to be constant pressure, lack of rules, and managerial harassment; therefore, this all results in foodservice industry employees to suffer mentally.

In addition, one of the biggest studies of such matter was conducted in US by Mental Health America (MHA) in 2017. As, after conducting a study for two continuous years, by surveying 17,000 employees in 19 industries, it was found that restaurant industry was the third worst industry to work in linked with high rate of mental suffering of employees. Not just this, in 2015 research by Substance Abuse and Mental Health Service found that employees in restaurants have shown high rate of drug and alcohol consumption, all related to mental health states of the workers. Similarly, a study conducted in 2018 by American Journal of Epidemiology found that restaurant employees, usually ones getting tips have higher risk of depression, insomnia and stress. As already seen from the findings mentioned, food and beverage industry employees are going through mental crisis of different kinds.

Prevalence and Types of Mental Health Problems Among Food and Beverage Sector Workers. It

is a very known actuality that food and beverage employees, especially ones working at restaurants are in a very stressful environment. There are several reasons for them to be in constant stress and even feel anxious such as due to low income [4], very long working hours [6] that all result in increased stress rate among [12,13]. Moreover, workplace bullying [5] as well as high expectations from supervisors/managers should be included in list of factors that cause mental pressure to food and beverage sector workers [14]. Not to mention the sick days of restaurant employees on which they are forced to work very frequently without any support whether it is financially or mentally [4]. Furthermore, due to many chefs being aggressive causes the environment in the back of house section of restaurant to be more stressful [15]. On the other hand, another study conducted found high prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress among waiters in restaurant [23]. Besides, another research done in Lebanon bakery store found that almost 50 percent of its employees had poor mental state, as they had various mental disorders, which once again indicates how negative is the mental state of employees in food and beverage sector [24].

Job Demands in Food and Beverage Sector and Their Link to Mental Health. As a part of service industry, food and beverage sector is dangerously stressful for people working in this sector, that is found according to a study done by Chinese scholars in 2015. The reason behind it is that the food industry jobs have many job demands that require employees to have many different things to balance at the same time. Such as speed, organized thought, perfection, quickness, and many more. Moreover, on top of all these requirements, employees are facing lots of difficulties as very often

their wages are cut, working hours are increased, can be called to work in unpredictable hours and even days [16,17,18,19].

In addition, job demands in this industry do not just include these issues, as, in many jobs in food and beverage sector, there is an observed weak social and psychological conditions, employees have low job control, as they are trapped under the control and pressure of management that pushes its employees to engage in unhealthy amount of workload and conditions [20,21]. Besides, many jobs in food and beverage industry give employees not much control over job, no independence in decision making, lack of support from the side of the management and justice and rather assign employees with complex job demands which results in mental disorders among employees and eventually they quit the job [22].

Theoretical Framework: Utilizing the JDR Model to Examine Job Demands and Mental Health in Food and Beverage Sector. Theory of Job-Demand Resources (JD-R) model was created in 2006 by Arnold Bakker and Evangelia Demerouti [11]. Thus, after its creation, this theory has been widely used in studies in order to examine the impact of job-related factors and processes on well-being of employees [25]. As, the model itself indicates job demands as processes that require the worker to engage in physical and mental efforts that result employees to get depleted mentally or physically, while, on the other hand, job resources support the employee by making the work-related processes somehow easy to complete and also lead to personal growth or improvement [25]. In JD-R theory it is stated that when job resources (organisational support, trainings, co-worker and manager support, development programs etc) are low and job demands (high workload, emotional labour, work pressure, lack of control, physical efforts, unsafe work environment etc) are high, then this results in negative employee well-being. As, based on JD-R model, it was even stated that continuous job pressure due to high demands result in physical and mental depletion of employees [26]. Therefore, the JD-R theory was considered in this study in order to shed light on how perceived organizational support (POS) can buffer the negative effects of job demands on employee mental health in the food and beverage industry of Northern Cyprus.

Problem Definition & Objectives. Food and beverage industry is one of the oldest and biggest industries in the world, that is usually considered as a branch of tourism industry. Although this industry is

expanding non-stop and is considered to be one of the largest industries, unfortunately the employees of the food and beverage sector, especially ones on the lower working level, are prone to number of burden and difficulties. Some of these difficulties include harassment and unpaid sick days [4], bullying [5] forced overtime working with no pay [6]. Thus, this all might lead to mental health problems in many food and beverage industry workers such as drug addiction [7], depression [8], and also burnout which is also known as emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment [9]. Not just this, it was also found that food and beverage industry is the second industry in the list with the highest number of employees with depression [10]. Therefore, it becomes obvious that food and beverage industry is not as delightful and amusing as it may seem.

On the other hand, although studies based on tourism industry of North Cyprus has been studied a lot and continues to be researched, the food and beverage industry of the country, especially considering the mental health of the employees in Northern Cypriot food and beverage sector has not been researched exclusively, especially on foreign workers, who might add unique layer to this research, as they might face additional challenges compared to local employees.

Thereby, the main objective of this research is to:

1. To examine if job demands in North Cyprus's food service businesses influence the mental health of foreign employees.

2. To examine if job resources such as organizational support lowers the impact of job demands on employees' mental health in North Cyprus food service businesses.

3. To suggest strategies for food service business owners to come up with and to create healthy and supportive work environment in order to keep the mental health of employees in North Cyprus food and beverage healthy and supported.

Thus this study aimed at examining mentioned hypotheses, hence, receiving either rejection or support for these hypotheses based on the research findings.

H1: Job Demands have an impact on Mental Health.

H2: The negative relationship between job demands and employee mental health will be weaker for employees who perceive high levels of organizational support compared to those with low POS.

Figure. 1 Conceptual Model of Research

Above indicated research model demonstrates the hypotheses of the study along with the relationship of the variables utilized in this research. Independent Variables of *Unscheduled Work (UW)*, *Work Interference with Personal Life (WIP)*, *Work Pressure (WP)* and *Adverse Working Conditions (AWCs)*. Dependent variables of *Anxiety*, *Depression*, and *Emotional Exhaustion (EE)*. Interacting/Moderating variables of *Perceived Organizational Support (POS)*. Control Variables of *Respondent Demographics (Age & Gender)*.

Research Design & Target Population. This study aims to find the impact of job demands on mental health of foreign employees and food and beverage serving jobs around North Cyprus. Therefore, questionnaire is used in our study to gather data, especially because questionnaire is easy to collect data with and also cheap. Moreover, the respondents' anonymity is preserved, as it leads to more honest answers. Thereby, this research is a quantitative study with a descriptive research design. Target population for this research is foreign workers in food and beverage sector of North Cyprus. The reason why foreign workers are selected is due to foreigners bringing diversity to research results, which helps in reaching more generalizable and broad-based research findings and results. Furthermore, as food and beverage sector is a large-scale industry, survey participants were chosen from restaurants, coffee-houses, buffets, cafes and many other food and drink establishments. The data is gathered through non-probability sampling methods with a combination of snowball sampling and convenience sampling techniques. In order to get reliable and valid results, all the scales are taken from reputable journals and/or studies with high reliability and validity. In addition, certain demographic questions are included as well as several introductory questions regarding respondents' occupation, category of working establishment, years of work, age and gender. All the scales have Likert scale answer choices that are considered as ordinal. On the other hand, demographic and introductory questions are nominal. Data analysis was done on SPSS statistical

package due to its high reputation in academia and wide usage.

Findings. The findings of the study suggest that all the constructs of job demand that include *Unscheduled Work (UW)*, *Work Interference with Personal Life (WIP)*, *Work Pressure (WP)* and *Adverse Working Conditions (AWCs)* have an impact on mental health of employees that include constructs of *Anxiety*, *Depression*, and *Emotional Exhaustion (EE)*. Therefore, leading to approval of the Hypothesis 1 which implies that *Job Demands* have impact on *Mental Health*. Interestingly, the study findings demonstrated that all the constructs of job demand have an influence on mental health, therefore, suggesting that all the job demand types tested in the study had an influence on the mental health of the foreign food and beverage industry workers in North Cyprus. As, when checking the impact of each job demand variable on each mental health variable, it was found that each independent variable had an influence on each dependent variable used in the study. Moreover, apart from all this, when checking the interacting impact of *Perceived Organizational Support (POS)*, to know whether it lowers the impact of job demands on mental health, it was found that employees who receive organizational support demonstrated low mental health issues than ones without organizational support, suggesting that *POS (Perceived Organizational Support)* acts as a buffer and lowers the impact of job demands on mental health, thus, supporting Hypothesis 2 which suggests the relationship between job demands and employee mental health will be weaker for employees who perceive high levels of organizational support compared to those with low *POS*. Therefore, all the hypotheses of the study were supported by the research findings after the analysis on the responses given by the foreign food and beverage sector employees in North Cyprus. Moreover, as it was found that perceived organizational support decreases the impact of job demands on mental health of employees, the *JD-R* theory has been supported as well. On the other hand, based on the research findings, in order for employees

to have healthier and better mental health, it is important and advisable for food and beverage sector businesses to lower the amount of job demands. Hence, creating positive environment, lowering the work pressure, making work conditions more bearable and light as well as giving employees more time for personal life would be beneficial for the workers to maintain healthy mental condition. Furthermore, as the results suggest, due to perceived organizational support decreasing the impact of job demands on mental health, it is also advisable for food and beverage businesses to show more support to their employees, as it helps them with overcoming the job difficulties and reduces the negative complications of the job on their wellness and health.

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